

Near-Field Beamfocusing with polarized antennas

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Abstract—One of the challenges in future 6G wireless networks is how to handle a massive number of terminals. Recently, extremely large antenna array (ELAA or XL-MIMO) has emerged as a potential enabler. It increases the number of spatial transmission modes and focus the transmission into a small region, because the communication is carried out in the *near-field* region and a large number of antenna elements are exploited. This work explores if the adoption of antenna elements with multiple polarizations could enhance the system performance in the *near-field*. We concentrate on a simple scenario consisting of a Uniform Linear Array (ULA) with $2M + 1$ antennas and a single-antenna user equipment (UE). We demonstrate that the number of spatial streams increases up to 3 in the *near-field* of a Line of Sight (LoS) channel when there are antennas with 3 dipoles (*tripole* antenna), but in the *far-field* the spatial streams tends to be 2, due to the deficient rank of the channel. We provide an analytical approximation of the achievable rate, that allow us to derive approximations of the optimal antenna spacing and antenna size in terms of maximizing the achievable rate.

Index Terms—XL-MIMO, ELAA, near-field communications, polarized multi-antenna communications

I. INTRODUCTION

Conventional wireless communication designs have traditionally assumed that radio waves are received in the *far-field* region, where the propagating wave front is essentially a plane. Enlarging the aperture array allows increasing the number spatial transmitting modes up to $\nu = K$ even in the Line of Sight (LoS) channel given that the antenna separation at the transmitter and receiver side satisfies the *Rayleigh spacing* criterion, $\Delta_T \Delta_R = \frac{D\lambda}{K}$ when both, transmitter and receiver, are equipped with K antennas [1]. The benefits of using MIMO-surface or MIMO antenna array are investigated in [2], and an upper bound on the capacity of LoS MIMO channel is provided in [3] which is attained with uniform linear arrays (ULA) by means of physically rotating the ULA depending on the signal to noise ratio (SNR).

With the advent of Extremely Large Antenna Arrays (ELAA), also referenced to in the literature as Large Intelligent Surfaces (LIS) or eXtra Large (XL)-MIMO, the *far-field* assumption can hardly be met, and the propagation wave front becomes spherical. The *near-field* paradigm offers new

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opportunities to exploit the wireless medium that have not been considered in conventional wireless system designs. For example, in the *near-field* region it is possible to use beamforming to focus energy on a spatial region (i.e. *beamfocusing*) rather than steered it into a specific direction [4], [5]. This property enables large throughput gains in wireless networks by drastically reducing interference among terminals, see [6] to review the latest advances. An interesting possibility to increase the spectral efficiency of the ELAA configuration without increasing the total transmission area is to employ multiple polarizations [7]–[9]. The analysis of the electromagnetic propagation phenomena reveals that inter-polarization interference may significantly affect the behavior of the resulting XL-MIMO channel. The attained spectral efficiency in uplink of this type of polarized XL-MIMO architecture is addressed in [10], elucidating that the polarization mismatch can significantly degrade the spectral efficiency.

Fig. 1. Scenario configuration. Transmitter is based on a ULA with $2M + 1$ antenna elements. These elements can be based on: 1 dipole, 2 dipoles or 3 dipoles (in the figure). The UE has a single antenna element.

This paper aims to investigate the use of additional polarizations in a ULA-based XL-MIMO system, see Fig. 1, when the communication is carried out in the *near-field* region, revisiting the results of [2], [3] derived for the *far-field*. Different from [9], [10], we will not make simplifying assumptions on the electromagnetic propagation conditions, leading us to increase the spatial transmission modes as a function of employed polarized antenna. To simplify the analysis, we will concentrate on the performance of infinitesimal dipoles, for which the total dimension of the antenna is much lower than the operative wavelength. The main contributions are:

- We demonstrate that the spatial transmission modes are $\nu = 3$ when a single-antenna UE is in the *near-field* region, and there are *tripole* antennas (i.e. 3 dipoles) at the receiver or transmitter side. We provide an approximation for the achievable rate at high SNR and the optimal antenna spacing, see Lemma IV.1.
- When antennas consist of 2 dipoles, the maximum achievable rate is obtained when all antenna elements are compacted as much as possible. Consequently, enlarging the ULA encompass a degradation of the achievable rate for a given UE, but it enhances the focusing capability, i.e. reducing the generated interference to unintended UEs. On the other hand, using a *tripole* antenna allows having gains in both cases, achievable rate and focusing capability.
- When the UE is placed on the *far-field* region, the use of *tripole* antennas do not provide any benefits compared with the 2-dipole antennas, because the channel matrix tends to be rank-deficient with degree 2, see Lemma IV.2.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a single-user XL-MIMO scenario as it is depicted in in Fig. 1. The transmitter is a XL-ULA equipped with $2M + 1$ antenna elements at $(0, 0, 0)$. The antenna separation between antennas is denoted by Δ_T . On the other hand, a single-antenna UE is placed at coordinates $(0, 0, D)$. With the objective of exploiting multiple polarizations the antenna elements can consist of: 3 dipoles or *tripole* antenna (3 polarizations), 2 dipoles (2 polarizations) or 1 dipole (1 polarization). Notice that each of the selected options impacts in the number of radio frequency (RF) units required on the system. The distance between the m th transmit antenna element and receive antenna element is given by,

$$\mathbf{r}_m = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ m\Delta_T \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ D \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{r}_m^2 = \mathbf{r}_m^H \mathbf{r}_m, \quad \hat{\mathbf{r}}_m = \frac{1}{r_m} \mathbf{r}_m$$

Taking into account the Green function introduced in electromagnetic theory, see [11], that provides the electric field at the receive antenna position due to a current source on the m th transmitting element, the equivalent channel matrix under the assumption of infinitesimal tripole antennas is given by,

$$\mathbf{H}_m = j \frac{\eta}{2\lambda} \frac{\exp(-j \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} r_m)}{r_m} \mathbf{P}_m \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_m = \mathbf{I} - \hat{\mathbf{r}}_m \hat{\mathbf{r}}_m^H + \mathbf{\Psi}_m \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{\Psi}_m = \frac{\lambda(j2\pi r_m - \lambda)}{(2\pi r_m)^2} (\mathbf{I} - 3\hat{\mathbf{r}}_m \hat{\mathbf{r}}_m^H) \quad (4)$$

Let us remark that $\mathbf{\Psi}_m \approx \mathbf{0}$ even for short distances, so that matrix $\mathbf{P}_m \in \mathcal{C}^{3 \times 3}$, tends to be an orthogonal projection matrix to the direction defined by $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_m$, and satisfying,

$$\mathbf{P}_m \mathbf{P}_m^H = \mathbf{P}_m \quad (5)$$

If the type of the transmit and receive antenna elements had different polarization, the channel matrix can be written as,

$$\bar{\mathbf{H}}_m = \mathbf{H}_m (1 : r_{pol}, 1 : t_{pol}) \quad (6)$$

with $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_m \in \mathcal{C}^{r_{pol} \times t_{pol}}$. Finally, the equivalent channel matrix for the XL-MIMO ULA with $M_t = 2M + 1$ antenna becomes,

$$\mathbf{H}_{eq} = (\bar{\mathbf{H}}_M \dots \bar{\mathbf{H}}_m \dots \bar{\mathbf{H}}_1) \quad (7)$$

with $\mathbf{H}_{eq} \in \mathcal{C}^{r_{pol} \times t_{pol}(2M+1)}$. The received signal is defined by,

$$\mathbf{y} = \sqrt{\rho} \mathbf{H}_{eq} \mathbf{F} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{w} \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{C}^{r_{pol} \times 1}$ denotes the received signal, ρ is the SNR, $\mathbf{H}_{eq} \in \mathcal{C}^{r_{pol} \times t_{pol} M_t}$, (7), represents the equivalent channel matrix, $\mathbf{F} \in \mathcal{C}^{t_{pol} M_t \times n_s}$ defines the precoding matrix to transmit n_s symbols, which are defined by $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{C}^{n_s \times 1}$. Finally, $\mathbf{w} \in \mathcal{C}^{r_{pol} \times 1}$ represents the Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) vector of unitary power.

III. RANK OF THE CHANNEL

The number of spatial transmission modes is connected with the rank of the channel matrix, which is determined by the number of non-zero eigenvalues. The eigenvalues can be derived by analyzing the Gramian of the channel matrix,

$$\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{H}_{eq} \mathbf{H}_{eq}^H = \left(\frac{\eta}{2\lambda} \right)^2 \sum_{m=-M}^M \frac{\mathbf{P}_m \mathbf{P}_m^H}{r_m^2} \quad (9)$$

with $\mathbf{W} \in \mathcal{C}^{r_{pol} \times r_{pol}}$. If transmitter and receiver are equipped with tripole antennas ($t_{pol} = r_{pol} = 3$), matrix \mathbf{W} becomes,

$$\mathbf{W}^{3 \times 3} = \begin{pmatrix} D^2 \beta_0 + \Delta_T^2 \beta_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & D^2 \beta_0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \Delta_T^2 \beta_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

with,

$$\beta_0 = \sum_{m=-M}^M \frac{1}{r_m^4} = \sum_{m=-M}^M \frac{1}{(D^2 + m^2 \Delta_T^2)^2} \quad (11)$$

$$\beta_1 = \sum_{m=-M}^M \frac{m^2}{r_m^4} = \sum_{m=-M}^M \frac{m^2}{(D^2 + m^2 \Delta_T^2)^2} \quad (12)$$

Lemma III.1. *The channel eigenvalues under $(r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = (3, 3)$ are the elements of the diagonal of $\mathbf{W}^{3 \times 3}$, (10), and they can be approximated as a function of $\epsilon = \frac{M \Delta_T}{D}$ by,*

$$\lambda_1^{3 \times 3}(\epsilon) = \left(\frac{\eta}{2\lambda} \right)^2 \frac{2M \arctan(\epsilon)}{D^2 \epsilon} \quad (13)$$

$$\lambda_2^{3 \times 3}(\epsilon) = \left(\frac{\eta}{2\lambda} \right)^2 \frac{M}{D^2} \left(\frac{\arctan(\epsilon)}{\epsilon} + \frac{1}{\epsilon^2 + 1} \right) \quad (14)$$

$$\lambda_3^{3 \times 3}(\epsilon) = \left(\frac{\eta}{2\lambda} \right)^2 \frac{M}{D^2} \left(\frac{\arctan(\epsilon)}{\epsilon} - \frac{1}{\epsilon^2 + 1} \right) \quad (15)$$

Proof. Assuming that $\Delta_T = \frac{D}{\omega}$, and M is large enough, the partial sums introduced in (11)-(12) can be approximated as a definite integral over $(-M, M)$, with closed-form expression,

$$\beta_0(\omega) \approx \frac{\omega}{D^4} \left(\arctan\left(\frac{M}{\omega}\right) + \frac{M\omega}{M^2 + \omega^2} \right) \quad (16)$$

$$\beta_1(\omega) \approx \frac{\omega^3}{D^4} \left(\arctan\left(\frac{M}{\omega}\right) - \frac{M\omega}{M^2 + \omega^2} \right) \quad (17)$$

Finally, we obtain the eigenvalues with the operations defined in the diagonal elements of (10) and using $\epsilon = \frac{M}{\omega} = \frac{M\Delta_T}{D}$. \square

When the antenna elements at the transmitter consists of 2 dipoles, but the receive antennas element is a *tripole*, $(r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = (3, 2)$ the dimensions of the channel differs from the previous case, see (5), leading to,

$$\mathbf{W}^{(3 \times 2)} = \begin{pmatrix} \beta_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & D^4 \beta_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & D^2 \Delta_T^2 \beta_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

with

$$\beta_2 = \sum_{m=-M}^M \frac{1}{r_m^2} = \sum_{m=-M}^M \frac{1}{(D^2 + m^2 \Delta_T^2)} \quad (19)$$

$$\beta_3 = \sum_{m=-M}^M \frac{1}{r_m^6} = \sum_{m=-M}^M \frac{1}{(D^2 + m^2 \Delta_T^2)^3} \quad (20)$$

$$\beta_4 = \sum_{m=-M}^M \frac{m^2}{r_m^6} = \sum_{m=-M}^M \frac{m^2}{(D^2 + m^2 \Delta_T^2)^3} \quad (21)$$

Lemma III.2. *The channel eigenvalues for configuration $(r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = (3, 2)$ can be approximated by,*

$$\lambda_1^{3 \times 2}(\epsilon) = \left(\frac{\eta}{2\lambda}\right)^2 \frac{2M}{D^2} \frac{\arctan(\epsilon)}{\epsilon} \quad (22)$$

$$\lambda_2^{3 \times 2}(\epsilon) = \left(\frac{\eta}{2\lambda}\right)^2 \frac{M}{4D^2} \left(\frac{3 \arctan(\epsilon)}{\epsilon} + \frac{3\epsilon^2 + 5}{(\epsilon^2 + 1)^2} \right) \quad (23)$$

$$\lambda_3^{3 \times 2}(\epsilon) = \left(\frac{\eta}{2\lambda}\right)^2 \frac{M}{4D^2} \left(\frac{\arctan(\epsilon)}{\epsilon} + \frac{\epsilon^2 - 1}{(\epsilon^2 + 1)^2} \right) \quad (24)$$

Proof. Follow the same steps as in *proof* of Lemma III.1, but using the closed-form solutions from (19),(20) and (21). \square

Finally, for a 2-dipoles-based antennas, $(t_{pol}, r_{pol}) = (2, 2)$, the maximum of the rank of the channel is 2.

Lemma III.3. *The channel eigenvalues under the configuration $(t_{pol}, r_{pol}) = (2, 2)$ are approximated by,*

$$\lambda_1^{2 \times 2}(\epsilon) = \left(\frac{\eta}{2\lambda}\right)^2 \frac{2M}{D^2} \frac{\arctan(\epsilon)}{\epsilon} \quad (25)$$

$$\lambda_2^{2 \times 2}(\epsilon) = \left(\frac{\eta}{2\lambda}\right)^2 \frac{M}{4D^2} \left(\frac{3 \arctan(\epsilon)}{\epsilon} + \frac{3\epsilon^2 + 5}{(\epsilon^2 + 1)^2} \right) \quad (26)$$

Proof. It can be shown that Gramian matrix \mathbf{W} in (9) becomes diagonal, having as diagonal elements the same that are presented in position (1,1) and (2,2) in (18). Therefore, the eigenvalues depends on (19) and (20). \square

IV. OPTIMAL ULA SIZE

Section III addressed how the rank of the channel matrix is influenced by number of employed polarizations (r_{pol}, t_{pol}) , the distance D , the number of transmit antenna elements $M_t = 2M + 1$ and their separation Δ_T . This section examines which is the optimal transmitting ULA size for each combination of considered polarizations, based on the information-theoretic capacity metric or achievable rate. When

the transmit precoder \mathbf{F} is based the right singular vectors of \mathbf{H}_{eq} , while a linear receiver based on the left singular vectors \mathbf{H}_{eq} is used at the UE, the achievable rate is described by,

$$C(\rho) = \sum_{n=0}^{r_{pol} N_r} \log_2 \left(1 + \rho \left[\frac{1}{\gamma} - \frac{1}{\sigma_n^2(\mathbf{H}_{eq})} \right]^+ \sigma_n^2(\mathbf{H}_{eq}) \right) \quad (27)$$

where γ denotes the water-level for the power allocation, $[z]^+ = \min(0, z)$, ρ is the SNR, and $\sigma_n^2(\cdot)$ consider the eigenvalues of \mathbf{H}_{eq} that have been presented in section III. The number of spatial transmission modes, i.e. spatial modes with non-zero power allocation, is defined by the number of degrees of freedom (DoF),

$$\nu = \lim_{\rho \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log 2^{C(\rho)}}{\log(\rho)} \quad (28)$$

Lemma IV.1. *Having one ULA with $M_t = 2M + 1$ antenna elements using polarizations $t_{pol} = \{2, 3\}$, and one UE with polarization $r_{pol} = \{2, 3\}$, the maximum achievable rate at high SNR is approximated by,*

$$C = C_0(\rho, M, D) + \alpha \left(\frac{M\Delta_T^*}{D} \right) \quad (29)$$

with

$$C_0(\rho, M, D) = \begin{cases} 3 \log_2 \left(\frac{\eta}{2\lambda} \right)^2 \frac{M}{D^2} \frac{\rho}{3} & (r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = (3 \times 3) \\ 3 \log_2 \left(\frac{\eta}{2\lambda} \right)^2 \frac{M}{4D^2} \frac{\rho}{3} & (r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = (3 \times 2) \\ 2 \log_2 \left(\frac{\eta}{2\lambda} \right)^2 \frac{M}{4D^2} \frac{\rho}{2} & (r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = (2 \times 2) \end{cases}$$

and

$$\alpha \left(\frac{M\Delta_T^*}{D} \right) = \begin{cases} -0.7794 & (r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = (3 \times 3) \\ 4.6339 & (r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = (3 \times 2) \\ \approx 0 & (r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = (2 \times 2) \end{cases}$$

The optimal transmit antenna separation is given by,

$$\Delta_T^* = \begin{cases} 0.9058 \frac{D}{M} & (r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = (3 \times 3) \\ 0.7144 \frac{D}{M} & (r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = (3 \times 2) \\ \approx 0 & (r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = (2 \times 2) \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

Proof. The achievable rate at high SNR follows the expression presented in (29). The second term, α , depends on the polarization (r_{pol}, t_{pol}) and $\epsilon = \frac{M\Delta_T}{D}$ by,

$$\alpha^{3 \times 3}(\epsilon) = \log_2 \left(2\zeta \left(\zeta + \frac{1}{\epsilon^2 + 1} \right) \left(\zeta - \frac{1}{\epsilon^2 + 1} \right) \right) \quad (31)$$

$$\alpha^{3 \times 2}(\epsilon) = \log_2 \left(8\zeta \left(3\zeta + \frac{3\epsilon^2 + 5}{(\epsilon^2 + 1)^2} \right) \left(\zeta + \frac{\epsilon^2 - 1}{(\epsilon^2 + 1)^2} \right) \right) \quad (32)$$

$$\alpha^{2 \times 2}(\epsilon) = \log_2 \left(8\zeta \left(3\zeta + \frac{3\epsilon^2 + 5}{(\epsilon^2 + 1)^2} \right) \right) \quad (33)$$

with $\zeta = \frac{\arctan(\epsilon)}{\epsilon}$. Since the maximum only depends on variable ϵ , the optimization can be done numerically. Fig. 2 presents how the $\alpha^{r_{pol} \times t_{pol}}$ is subject to ϵ . When $(r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = \{(3, 3), (3, 2)\}$, α has a maximum for certain ϵ , while for $(r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = (2, 2)$, $\alpha^{2 \times 2}$ is a decreasing function, elucidating

Fig. 2. Evaluation of function α presented in (31),(32),(33)

that the achievable rate under configuration $(r_{pol}, t_{pol}) = (2, 2)$ always decrease if antenna separation increases. \square

Lemma IV.1 remarks the importance of tripolarized antennas to increase the number of DoF in the *near-field* ($\nu^{3 \times 3} = \nu^{3 \times 2} = 3$) with respect the case of having just 2-dipole antennas ($\nu^{2 \times 2} = 2$). Nevertheless, when the UE is too far from the antenna array and ($\Delta_T \neq \Delta_T^*$), the following lemma shows that $\nu^{3 \times 3} = \nu^{3 \times 2} = \nu^{2 \times 2} = 2$.

Lemma IV.2. *Tripole antennas are only beneficial in the near-field region because in the far-field the the rank of the channel matrix with dimensions $r_{pol} \times t_{pol} M_t$ tend to be 2.*

Proof. Evaluating the expressions given in Lemma III.1, III.2 and III.3 and assuming $D \gg \Delta_T M$ and $D \gg 0$, we obtain,

$$\lambda_{1,FF}^{3 \times 3} = \lambda_{1,FF}^{3 \times 2} = \lambda_{1,FF}^{2 \times 2} = \lambda_{2,FF}^{3 \times 3} = \lambda_{2,FF}^{3 \times 2} = \lambda_{2,FF}^{2 \times 2} \approx \left(\frac{\eta}{2\lambda}\right)^2 \frac{2M}{D^2}$$

$$\lambda_{3,FF}^{3 \times 3} = \lambda_{3,FF}^{3 \times 2} \approx 0$$

where it is assumed that $\arctan(x) \approx x$ and $\epsilon^2 = \frac{M^2 \Delta_T^2}{D^2} \ll 1$ \square

V. RESULTS

We consider the scenario presented in Fig. 1 based on a single ULA with $M_t = 2M + 1$ antenna elements at $(0, 0, 0)$ and a single-antenna UE at $(0, 0, D)$. For the evaluation, we consider a carrier frequency of $f = 3$ GHz ($\lambda = 0.1$) and $\eta = 1$. Nevertheless, the antenna elements might have different number of polarizations, we reference each configuration in the following way:

- $(r_{pol} \times t_{pol}) = (3, 3)$: *tripole* antennas at UE and ULA
- $(r_{pol} \times t_{pol}) = (3, 2)$: *tripole* antenna at UE, but ULA equipped with 2-dipole antennas
- $(r_{pol} \times t_{pol}) = (2, 2)$: 2-dipole antennas at UE and ULA

Results are organized in three subsections. Section V-A will show how the eigenvalues of the channel under each configuration depends on the antenna separation, Δ_T . Section V-B will present the achievable rate obtained by a UE at

$(0, 0, D)$, elucidating the benefits of the polarized systems and which is the optimal dimension of the ULA. Finally, section V-C presents the *focusing* capabilities of the polarized ULA.

A. Eigenvalues of the channel matrix

Fig.3 illustrates the eigenvalues of matrix \mathbf{W} , (9), for the different polarization configurations. We compare the results obtained by simulation (solid lines) and the ones obtained with the expressions derived in Lemma III.1, Lemma III.2 and Lemma III.3 (dotted lines) when the UE is at $D = 5$ and there are $M_t = \{7, 31\}$ antenna elements. Results are obtained as a function on the antenna separation Δ_T . We verify that the analytical solutions tends to the simulated one when we increase M , that was one of the assumptions to get those expressions. Additionally, as the analytical expressions suggest: i) the first eigenvalue of the channel for all the configurations is the same ($\lambda_1^{3 \times 3} = \lambda_1^{3 \times 2} = \lambda_1^{2 \times 2}$), ii) the second eigenvalue of the configurations (2, 2) and (2, 3) are equal ($\lambda_2^{3 \times 2} = \lambda_2^{2 \times 2}$), but smaller than the first eigenvalue with configuration (3, 3) ($\lambda_2^{3 \times 3} \geq \lambda_2^{3 \times 2}$), and iii) first and second eigenvalues decreases when we increase Δ_T , but the third eigenvalue when the receive antenna has a tripole, i.e. configuration $\{(3, 3), (3, 2)\}$, is subject to Δ_T . Consequently, it is possible to increase the number of spatial transmission modes.

Fig. 3. Left) 1st eigenvalue, Center) 2nd eigenvalue, Right) 3rd eigenvalue obtained by simulation and analytically when UE is at $D = 5$ and there are $M_t = (7, 31)$ ($M = (3, 15)$).

B. Achievable rate

Fig. 4 presents the maximum achievable rate for a given SNR (ρ) under multiple polarization configurations when there are $M_t = 41$ antenna elements and UE is at $D = 5$. The maximum achievable rate is obtained by optimizing the antenna spacing Δ_T . The configurations (3, 3), (2, 2) show the largest gains in terms of achievable rate. Furthermore, at high SNR, the slope of the achievable rate, measured according to (28), attains $\nu = 3$. Likewise, we can observe that the approximations provided in Lemma IV.1 for the achievable rate at high SNR are very close to the simulated achievable rate when $\rho \geq 5$ dB. On the other hand, Fig. 5 depicts the ULA size where the achievable rate is maximum as a function of the SNR and the UE is at $D = \{3, 5\}$. Notice that the optimal

ULA sizes coincides with the values predicted using Lemma IV.1, i.e. $L_{ULA}^{3 \times 3} = 2M\Delta_T^* = 2 \times 0.9058D$ and $L_{ULA}^{3 \times 2} = 2 \times 0.7144D$. Interestingly, the obtained achievable rate with configuration (3, 2) is close to the maximum one (3, 3), but requiring an smaller ULA size with only *tripole* antenna at the UE side.

Fig. 4. Optimized achievable rate (simulated and using approximation of Lemma IV.1) as a function of SNR (dB) with respect antenna separation (Δ_T). UE at $D = 5$. $M_t = 41$.

Fig. 5. Optimal size of the ULA (numerical optimization of Δ_T^*) for a UE with SNR $\rho = 20$ dB, $M_t = 41$. The predicted size is given by Lemma IV.1: $L_{ULA}^{3 \times 3} = 2 \times 0.9058D$ and $L_{ULA}^{3 \times 2} = 2 \times 0.7144D$.

C. Near-field beam-focusing

In previous subsections we have observed that we can increase the number of spatial transmission modes, ν , by using *tripole* antennas at the UE, thanks to the channel properties. However, once the precoder filter \mathbf{F} is designed for a certain UE, what is happening to the signal received in other positions?. In conventional *far-field* scenarios, it is known that the transmission is steered into a direction, so

all the UEs placed in the same direction will be able to receive the signal, and consequently, generating interference to unintended UEs. In order to evaluate this effect, we assume that we design the transmit filter \mathbf{F} for a terminal placed at $D = 5$, and we evaluate which is the achievable rate that might obtain a terminal placed in positions along the z -axis $(0, 0, D)$. If the polarized ULA is able to focus the transmission, we would expect that a UE, for example at $D = 10$, was not interfered by the signal intended to the UE at $D = 5$, so that measuring a very low achievable rate. In this regard, Fig. 6-Top) presents the achievable rate obtained when having $2M+1$ antenna elements at the ULA with a polarization configuration (2×2) , total antenna size of $L_{ULA}^{2 \times 2} = 0.5$ m, and a transmit precoder designed for a UE at $D = 5$. For this configuration we could increase the antenna size, see Fig. 6-bottom), and results show that the signal can be slightly focused at the position of the UE. This is a consequence of having a large ULA, operating in the *near-field* region and the precoder takes into account the sphere wave propagation. Nevertheless, this comes at the cost of reducing the maximum achievable rate at the point of interest. Notice that Lemma IV.1 states that for (2×2) , (1×1) polarization configuration the transmitting antennas should be packed as much as possible, otherwise a reduction in achievable rate is obtained.

Fig. 6. Evaluation of the achievable rate as a function of the distance $(0, 0, d)$ when transmit precoders are selected for a UE placed at $(0, 0, 5)$. SNR $\rho = 20$ dB. Top) configuration (2×2) with $L_{ULA} = 0.5$ m, Bottom) configuration (2×2) with $L_{ULA} = 9.058$ m

On the other hand, Fig. 7 presents the achievable rate obtained when *tripole* antennas are considered, that allows increasing the number of spatial transmission modes from $\nu = 2$ to $\nu = 3$. The configuration (3×3) and (2×2) are considered in Fig. 7-Top) and Fig. 7-Bottom), respectively. In both cases, we have set the antenna spacing according to Lemma IV.1, leading to different ULA sizes. It can be observed that the maximum achievable rate of each configuration is very similar, but the region where the signal is focused is slightly different. For example with $M = 100$, the region where the achievable

rate is at 10 bits/s/Hz below the maximum in configuration (3×3) is in the region $d \in (4.6, 5.35)$, while for the (3×2) configuration is $d \in (4.55, 5.45)$.

Fig. 7. Evaluation of the achievable rate as a function of the distance $(0, 0, d)$ when transmit precoders are selected for a UE placed at $(0, 0, 5)$. SNR $\rho = 20$ dB. Top) configuration (3×3) with $L_{\text{ULA}} = 9.058$ m, Bottom) configuration (3×2) with $L_{\text{ULA}} = 7.144$ m.

We have optimized the ULA size in order to maximize the achievable rate at a given distance and SNR, and the signal can be focused for a certain region, but still the unintended UEs at $d \neq D_{\text{UE}}$ are receiving a important interference signal. Making good use of the *peak* in terms of achievable rate, we could reduce the transmitting power to reduce the interference signal, important aspect from a system point of view and allowing the multi-user transmission, at the cost of reducing the achievable rate at the UE's position. Fig. 8 depicts the achievable rate at SNR, $\rho = 10$ dB, illustrating that the signal is more concentrated around the UE's position, while reducing the generated interference (i.e. low achievable rate at positions $d \neq D$). The configuration with *tripole* antennas are able to improve the achievable rate using 2-dipole antennas by a factor 27%.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work has investigated under which circumstances a transmitter consisting of a single ULA equipped with $2M + 1$ antennas is able to focus the signal into a given region. Each antenna element can have: i) 1-dipole, ii) 2-dipoles, or iii) 3-dipoles (tripole). By using antennas with 2 polarizations at transmitter and receiver side, we can focus the transmitted signal by increasing the ULA size at the cost of reducing the maximum achievable rate. However, if a tripole antenna is considered, at least at the receiver side, we have shown that is possible to increase the number of spatial transmission modes up to $\nu = 3$ and the achievable rate, see Lemma IV.1, and focus the transmission. In this latter case the ULA size tends to $L^{3 \times 2} = 2 \times 0.9058 \times D$ and $L^{3 \times 2} = 2 \times 0.7144 \times D$ if the

Fig. 8. Evaluation of the achievable rate as a function of the distance $(0, 0, d)$ when precoder is designed for a UE placed at $D = 5$. SNR $\rho = 10$ dB.

antenna elements at the ULA are tripoles (3 polarizations) or only have 2 dipoles (2 polarizations), respectively.

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